

Literature Review on Control Techniques of AC-DC Boost Converter

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Abstract

The paper present reviews on various control techniques employed on to AC-DC boost converter. The control techniques are studied in general as well as with respect to the field of application. The paper also particularly reviews the control techniques of AC-DC boost converter which was employed as power factor correction device.

Index Terms: AC-DC boost converter, Power factor correction, linear controller, non-linear controller.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent days the power electronics and drives is widely used and reduce the size of the drive system. The various converter methodologies such as AC-DC, DC-DC, DC-AC, AC-AC and generate high

gain. The converter is used in high dc components such as UPS, battery storage device, electric vehicle etc. The solid-state devices have some merits and suffer from different power quality problems like harmonic injection, poor power factor, switching transients etc. In rectifier has generate high ripple output at load side and it will reduced by using filter and used in high power application. Passive, active and hybrid filters are often employed to meet the requirement. However, filters are huge in nature and also endure from losses. Also, the rating of such filters is similar to that of load. The need for robust and flexible operations led to the addition of buck, boost and buck-boost converters after the rectifier stage of AC-DC converters. The AC-DC boost converters, a combination of rectifier and step up dc chopper, is predictable to operate with less harmonic generation, better power factor, good dc regulations, quick response to load and grid conditions, reduces electromagnetic interference etc. The AC-DC boost converters are used widely in varied application ranging from small rated implant devices to high power rated nuclear fusion equipments. Similar to other converters, various solid state switches like thyristor, MOSFET, IGBT and GTO used in AC-DC boost converters were reported for their respective features like high switching rates, high power rating etc. Similarly, AC-DC boost converters operating at few 1000 Hz to 1 or 2 MHz had been reported in literature. The AC-DC boost converter are also extensively used in electric drives, UPS, SMPS and Power factor corrector devices. Although many review papers had come out on converters review papers on AC-DC boost converter are rarely seen. Hence in this present paper, an attempt had been made, particularly reviewing the control techniques performed on to AC-DC boost converters. The section II briefly describes the AC-DC boost converters topologies available in the literature. Various control techniques and applications of AC-DC boost converters are reviewed in section III and IV, respectively followed by conclusion.

2 AC-DC BOOST CONVERTER DESIGN TOPOLOGIES

The AC- DC rectifier has used in various application such as medical, industrial and nuclear fusion. In ac-dc conversion utilizes in

adjustable speed drive, switched mode power supply, unified power supply and battery energy storage. In Diode Bridge rectifier has some demerits such as less power quality by introducing current harmonics causing voltage distortion and less power factor at ac side [1]. The AC-DC converter has convert either in single stage or two stages. The converter comprises the transformer, mutual inductance and switches. The single stage power converter is shown in fig 1. The design of single stage power conversion has high power factor correction with high efficiency and output voltage regulation.

Figure 1: Diode Rectifier Circuit

The diode bridge rectifier is mostly used for improving PFC. The diode bridge rectifier is simple and unity power factor control method using proper control method. in diode rectifier has high switching losses and reduce the efficiency. In high switching frequency the boost diode has reverse recovery problem, diode turn off losses and generates high EMI noise. The bridge less Cuk converter has converts the AC-DC and attains the zero current switching for pulse width modulation. The bridgeless Cuk converter is shown in figure 2. The Single stage converters are gaining popularity nowadays for its robustness and simple topology. Moreover single stage boost converter works on the principle of controlling the input ac current unlike two stage converter where the output ac is tuned according to the requirements [2]. Hence single stage AC-DC boost converter is highly utilized in power factor correctors where the harmonic reduction is prime concern.

Figure 2: Bridgeless Cuk Converter

The single phase isolated ac-dc converter with power factor correction used in application such as battery electric vehicles and plug in electric vehicles. The AC-DC boost converter works with wide range of power and voltage ratings. For instance, boost converter used in medical application was in the range of milli watts whereas the rating of boost converter used in nuclear fusion was in the range of kilo watts. Also the operating switching frequency of the boost converter varies widely from 1000 Hz to 1 MHz [3]. High power rated boost converters are achieved either by using multi-cell or multilevel converters. Multilevel converters have the advantage of increasing the voltage rating of the converter as a whole without increasing the switching devices voltage rating. Also, the multilevel converters were reported for its reduced harmonic distortion in line current. However, the problem of packaging and neutral point potential imbalances limits the number of levels used in multilevel converter [4]. The bridgeless interleaved converter has two converter functions in parallel operation. The merits of interleaved converter high efficiency, reduces the input current ripple and less electromagnetic interference [5]. The bridgeless landsman converter has working in low switching frequency by commutating the brushless dc motor for decreasing the losses and generates effective power quality output [6].

3 CONTROL TECHNIQUES OF AC-DC BOOST CONVERTER

The unidirectional AC-DC boost converter has enhanced the power quality, loss reduction and noise and increased compactness. The converter has the combination of rectifier and dc chopper with filter and energy storage devices. The high frequency pulse width modulation and hysteresis controller has regulated the inner current loop and outer voltage loop for fast response and high power quality. The application of the unidirectional boost converter in electronic ballast, power supply, variable speed ac motor drives in fan, pumps and compressor [7]. The two device symmetrical unidirectional converter is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Unidirectional Symmetrical AC-DC Converter

Basic control

The converter employed with boost converter can be operated either as voltage fed or current fed converter where the output voltage or current is regulated respectively. Even though the current fed converter performs better as it directly controls the output current, voltage fed converter is generally preferred for its fast response and less complex control circuits. It is expected that the boost converter should respond faster in tracking changes either in grid or load. Also, the dc-link voltage should be under well regulated particularly during transients. In order to achieve faster responses, using the PI controller for producing the reference current and the input of PI controller is voltage error. The reference current is maintained to a particular limit and multiplied with sinusoidal voltage with unity magnitude for producing the sinusoidal current waveform [8]. The synchronous reference frame control method gives faster response in steady state condition; it failed to track the reference during transients. The reference controller has generated a unity power factor apart from complex computational issues and hence a new controller particular for maintaining a unity power factor, low cost and less computational time.

Even though, the parallel boost converter works at faster rate along with high efficiency, it suffers from the circulating currents as caused in any parallel connections. The complexity in designing such parallel boost converter increases further in case of synchronous reference frame controller as zero-axis current emerging out of circulating current is not reflected in synchronous reference frame controller [9].

B. Advanced Control

The complexity of AC-DC boost converters controller increases further because of the interdependency between the duty ratio of the converter and the state variables of the controller. This interdependency introduces a non-linearity in controller design equations.

Hence, an advanced controller such as non-linear controller based on Lyapunov control theory was developed [10].

Among various non-linear controllers, hysteresis controller was considered to have a fast dynamic response and low total harmonic distortion. However, hysteresis had a disadvantage of lack of appropriate control over the switching frequency variations.

Recent popular machine-learning controllers are considered as an effective tool in case of non-linear control system. Various machine-learning techniques are fuzzy logic, neural network, etc. Neural networks update their control strategies through continuous learning of present and past operating conditions of the system.

On the other hand, fuzzy controller works mainly based on the uncertainty of the system conditions. Compared to neural network controller, fuzzy controllers are highly robust and are easy to implement and integrate with the existing control system. In AC-DC boost converter based unity power factor rectifier was studied with both fuzzy logic and neural-network controllers [11].

C. Comparison of various Control techniques

The pulse width modulation utilize outer voltage control loop and inner current loop. The current controller compares the supply current and reference value. The merits of controller have to maintain the output voltage and enhance the power factor near unity. In interleaved converter has generates pulse using the triangular generator and PI output. The reference voltage is compared with output voltage and fed into PI. Linear and nonlinear model reference adaptive control (MRAC) methods are developed to control power factor (PF) and regulate output and neutral point voltages. The boost converter has three control methods has implemented in steady state of line-current harmonic distortion, efficiency, and PF and during transients such as load, utility disturbances, reactive power control, and dc-bus voltage tracking behaviour. In rectifier the circulating current is maintained by the pulse width modulation for controlling the grid current and rectifier output current. The PI based PWM has used to maintain the reference voltage and grid current. The circulating current control method is shown in figure 4.

and fed into the grid. The output voltage current of the converter has minimum ripple in supply frequency and has low bandwidth for decreasing the current distortion. The electric vehicle power conversion system has two sets of battery such as high voltage and 12V battery. The high voltage battery used for the purpose of traction and industrial. The 12V battery is used for testing purpose. In high-power applications, interleaving PFC stages can decrease inductor size as well as output capacitor ripple current. In this paper, two interleaved boost converters are used to execute the PFC stage. The full-bridge method is the most popular topology used for battery charges in the power range of a few kilowatts (15 kW). Since the switch ratings are optimized for the full-bridge topology, this topology is extensively used in industrial applications. High efficiency, high-power density, and more reliability are the well-known characteristics of rectifier. In resonant converter the zero voltage switching has increase the reactive current. Since the battery charger demands a very wide range of load variations, the design would result in a very large resonant tank and low-power density. In low power application the ZVS full bridge converter in auxiliary commutated network. In these converters, an auxiliary circuit is used to produce the reactive current for the full-bridge switches. The bandwidth of the rectifier is increased by using the notch filter for reducing the harmonic ripple. The dead band has maintained the input power instead of bus voltage. The DC-bus voltage is adaptively controlled based on the power demand from the charging curve of the battery. The control system basically optimizes the amount of reactive power required for the DC-DC full bridge converter stage for different load conditions.

C. Power Quality Improvement

The power factor improvement method has become increasingly important since a number of regulations that are used to limit harmonic injection to the power utilities have been performed. The active and passive power factor correction methods are used in converter application. Active PF has classified has both single and double stage method. The quasi active power factor correction circuit diagram is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Circuit diagram of quasi active PFC

The stages of power factor correction and enhance the output response using independent control method. The operation stage of quasi active network is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Operation of Quasi Active PFC

The main disadvantage of this method are its comparatively higher cost and larger size resulted from its complicated power stage topology and control circuits, particularly in low power applications. A scheme combines the PFC cell and dc/dc power conversion cell into one stage, and typically uses only one controller and shares power switches.

The high-power factor ac-dc converter with a step up converter functioning in the discontinuous conduction mode (DCM) and the critical conduction mode (CRM) power factor of the converter in DCM and CRM are derived as a function of the circuit factor. For attain high power factor, the ac-dc converters want sensors for identify input voltage and current. Moreover, these converters need multipliers in order to regulate the output voltages. Therefore the circuit configuration tends to become complicated. The step up chopper is used in the ac-dc converter and it is function under a reactor-current discontinuous conduction mode the high

power factor can be achieved with a simple circuit configuration without sensing the input voltages and currents. A single stage fly boost converter design combining the conventional flyback and boost converter was proposed. It was claimed that higher efficiency was obtained by transferring a part of input power directly to output using only few components. The boost converter configuration is widely used for T active power factor correction (PFC) because its input current is continuous and can be shaped to track a desired waveform with minimum conducted noise. A feed forward PFC control method which eliminates the need for instantaneous input current measurement and replaces it with a slower load current measurement is described. This control method is based on the notion that as the desired input current waveform is known a priori and deterministic, viz., a sine wave in proportion to the input voltage waveform, it can be initially modelled in the control structure. Using the internal model of the sine wave, a periodic control signal with double the line frequency is generated and is used for modulating a constant frequency pulse width modulation (PWM) signal which effects the switching control of the PFC. dynamic model of the PFC boost converter, a nonlinear control law is proposed which generates the sine wave-template signal using the sensed PFC output voltage, the output current and the input voltage as input variables. Using an internal model of the AC input voltage waveform, the control scheme generates a periodically varying duty cycle control signal for the modulation of a constant frequency PWM signal which controls the boost converter power switch. The constraint that the duty cycle can assume values only below unity imposes limitations on the achievable line current wave shaping. the control parameters of the duty cycle control signal are initially computed and set to their approximate steady-state values using the sensed input and output voltages and the load current. Given that a major element used in the proposed PFC control scheme is the internal model of the sine wave and the load measurement is used only to provide further shaping of the duty cycle derived from this internal model, a natural question which arises is whether the load current can be completely eliminated as a measurement and replaced with an estimate. This appears feasible from a continuous measurement of the output voltage profile. For example, at the zero-crossings of the input voltage waveform, most of the load current is drawn

from the output filter capacitor and hence the load current can be estimated by measuring the droop in the output voltage in the neighbourhood of these zero-crossings.

The quasi active method has enhanced the power factor correction and reduces the harmonics. In discontinuous current mode attains the high performance in single stage power converter system. The discontinuous operation has minimum THD in input current compared to continuous operation. The first half cycle operates in both the mode such as continuous and discontinuous mode. In discontinuous operation the inductor current is less with minimum voltage. The continuous operating mode the input voltage is high with increase the inductor current.

5 CONCLUSION

The ac-dc converter has analysed in various pulse width modulation. The control method and design of the converter has enhances the efficiency and power factor correction. The voltage and current ripple is reduced by using the various PWM based converter methodology. The interleaved converter has improve the performance and used in low power application with three phase circuit for high output.

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